

ISic1575

I.Sicily inscription 1575

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stucco (on tuff)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Πριμίων [---]

2. χάρε

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284881

EDR 108281

EDCS 41300085

PHI 175699

Bibliography

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Rocco, B. 1970. Due iscrizioni fenicie da Mozia. *Sicilia Archeologica*. 3: 27-33. At 28
Vento, M. 2000. Le stele dipinte di Lilibeo. Marsala. At 49 tav.84

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